

THE ORGANIZATIONAL ATTRACTIVENESS AND JOB SATISFACTION OF INSTRUCTORS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS WHO WORKS IN DIFFERENT REGIONS

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Abstract:

In our research which is made in order to examine the organizational attractiveness and job satisfaction of instructors of physical education and sports who works in different regions in terms of different factors, there are 60 instructors who are 12 women and 48 men and have different academic title and work in 7 universities in different regions of Turkey. According to the variance of academic title of instructors, they ,distribute as 5 associate professor (% 8,5), 18 assistant professor (%30,0), 17 instructors (%28,3), 8 lecturers (% 13,3), 12 research assistant (% 20,0). While choosing of the universities, it is looked youngest universities and the number of instructors is least. “Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale”, “Organizational Attractiveness” and “Demographic Information Form” are used. The points which are located of scale dimensions are evaluated between 1 and 5. According to the test results which are done in order to find out if there is a meaningful difference in terms of the variances of academic title, age, years of service, duration of administration, administrative task, lesson hours, marital status of the averages points of the organizational attractiveness, internal satisfaction, external satisfaction, general satisfaction of the instructors who participate the research, a meaningful difference has not been found. There is a weak, positive directional relation among the internal, external satisfaction and organizational attractiveness. There is a

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weak, positive directional relation between general satisfaction and organizational attractiveness.

Keywords: instructors, organizational attractiveness, employer attractiveness, job satisfaction

1. Introduction

In developing countries, due to the need for qualified manpower in different fields of occupation, value for higher education has been increasing day by day. Besides, the number of higher education institutions and the teaching staff working in these institutions are also increasing day by day. It is very important for instructors to provide job satisfaction and be happy to fulfill their duty out rightly. In 1998, Sergiovanni and Stratt stated the instructors' job satisfaction level's importance by pointing out the instructors' job satisfaction's correlation with students' academic performances. Nuances occurring when the worker compares his values and which one of these values becomes fact in what way determine the job satisfaction (Mc Cormic and Ilgen, 1980). Another definition is that job satisfaction is happiness or unhappiness from the workers' job.

Organizational attractiveness has an important role in the workers' workplace choice. Individuals tend to choose working in workplaces that they think attractive. Academicians and managers search ways to enhance the workers' performance and keep them in the business; and the need for organizational attractiveness has been increasing in order to accomplish these objectives. As a result of studies conducted in this context, it has been stated that organizational attractiveness has more influence than job satisfaction when the worker quits his job. If the worker's expectations overlap with his values, he abides by the organization and its mission and he provides satisfaction in his job. It is determined that physical conditions, payment, and reward system are also important in job satisfaction. Commitment to the organization, organizational attractiveness is important in providing business continuity. The workers' being in organizational attractiveness is not only important for business continuity but increasement in productivity of work as well.

2. Organizational Attractiveness

Recently, organizational attractiveness concept has been one of the emphasized topics. There are different opinions about organizational attractiveness. Tsai and his friends

(2012) defined that “Organizational attractiveness is the desire for following the work and accepting offers in that workplace.” Organizational attractiveness is the picture of desire in potential worker’s workplace in his brain (Öksüz, 2012:8). In other words, it expresses that organizational attractiveness is effective on the workers’ applying for a workplace and it is a situation that significantly effects the decision they are to make about this topic (Akçay, 2014: 177).

In his study, Öksüz (2012) analyzed the organizational attractiveness in terms of the candidates and stated factors affecting organizational attractiveness, factors affecting employer brand as work environment, payment and other material benefits, career opportunities and development, work and life balance, institution features, institution culture, product service brand, leadership, management and institutional social responsibility.

3. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is an emotional effect which occurs in the worker due to worker’s values towards his job and the factors that job embodies to the employer (Oshakgemi, 2000: 331). In other words, job satisfaction is the emotional factor that mental and financial elements create on the worker (Eren, 2004: 202). In another definition, job satisfaction has been defined as the situation of feeling likeable and positive incidents in the result of evaluating job or job experience (Brough and Frame, 2004: 9). It can also be expressed as the presence of emotional situations that allow individuals to confront what they enjoy when their eyes are on their work or experience (Luthans, 1992). Job satisfaction can also be explained as fulfilling the worker’s requests about the job within the workplace limits (Akçamete et. al., 2001).

4. Method

4.1 Population and Sample

In this study which is conducted to determine the job satisfaction levels of physical training and sports instructors of universities in different regions, descriptive research design has been used, which is frequently used in social sciences area (Büyüköztürk, Ş., Kılıç Çakmak, E, Akgün, Ö.E. Karadeniz, Ş. And Demirel, F. 2014). The population of this study consists of public universities in Turkey. The sample group consists of 12 female and 48 male instructors, who have different academic title, working at 7 universities in different region within academic year of 2015-2016; 60 instructors in total.

Purposeful sampling has been used in selection of universities in sample group of the research. For this reason, the most recent institutions within the region have been selected as the organization, particularly for the number of teaching staff. The regions training instructors for Physical Training and Sports are as follows: Batman University in Southeastern Anatolia region, Karabük University in Black Sea region, Bitlis Eren University in Eastern Anatolia region, Balıkesir University in Marmara region, Ahi Evran University in Central Anatolia region, Mehmet Akif University in Mediterranean region, Afyon Kocatepe University in Aegean region.

4.2 Data Collection Tool

In the research; there are demographic information in the first part, in the second part organizational attractiveness scale, and questions about job satisfaction scale in the third part. Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) which was developed by Weiss and his friends (1967) was used as a data collection tool for measuring job satisfaction. The adaptation of the scale into Turkish has been done by Baycan (Baycan, F.A., 1985). In this research, reliability co-efficient Cronbach alpha of Organizational attractiveness scale has been found as 0,671; reliability co-efficient of job satisfaction scale has been found as 0,883.

4.3 Statistical Analysis of the Data

The collected data has been analyzed by using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) for Windows 22.0 program. In data evaluation, number, percentage, mean, standard deviation has been used as descriptive statistical methods. Point of scale dimensions have been evaluated between 1 and 5. This gap has 4 points width. By equal dividing this width into 5, each width has been interpreted as follows: 1.00- 1.79 “very low”, 1.80- 2.59 “low”, 2.60- 3.39 “middle”, 3.40-4.19 “high”, 4.20-5.00 “very high” (http://www.istatistikanaliz.com/faktor_analizi.asp). Man Whitney-U Test for comparing quantitative continuous data between two independent groups, and Kruskal Whallis Test have been used for comparing more than two independent groups. In order to determine the difference after the Kruskal Whallis Test, Man Whitney-U Test has been used as adjunct. Spearman Correlation and regression analysis have been used between continuous variables of the research. The gathered findings have been evaluated at %95 confidence interval, and %5 significance level.

5. Findings and Commentary

Table 1: Range of Teaching Staff's Descriptive Features

Tables	Groups	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
School Worked	Bitlis Eren University	7	11,7
	Karabük University	7	11,7
	Batman University	10	16,7
	Afyon University	8	13,3
	Balıkesir University	8	13,3
	Burdur University	6	10,0
	Kırşehir University	14	23,3
	Total	60	100,0
Gender	Male	48	80,0
	Female	12	20,0
	Total	60	100,0
Academic Title	Associate Professor	5	8,3
	Assistant Professor	18	30,0
	Instructor	17	28,3
	Lecturer	8	13,3
	Research Assistant	12	20,0
	Total	60	100,0
Age	20-30	16	26,7
	31-40	27	45,0
	+ 40	17	28,3
	Total	60	100,0
Year of Service	1-5 years	25	41,7
	6-10 years	7	11,7
	11-15 years	16	26,7
	+ 15 years	12	20,0
	Total	60	100,0
Duration of Administration	None	32	53,3
	1-3 Years	17	28,3
	+ 3 Years	11	18,3
	Total	60	100,0
Administrative Task	Yes	22	36,7
	No	38	63,3
	Total	60	100,0
Lesson Hours	0	4	6,7
	0-15	17	28,3
	16-20	4	6,7
	21-25	10	16,7
	26-30	25	41,7
	Total	60	100,0
Marital Status	Married	43	71,7
	Single	17	28,3
	Total	60	100,0

According to the school variable, 7 (11,7%) of the teaching staff were from Bitlis Eren University, 7 (11,7%) were from Karabük University, 10 (16,7%) were from Batman University, 8 (13,3) Afyon University, 8 (13,3%) Balıkesir University, 6 (10,0%) Burdur University and 14 (23,3%) Kırşehir University.

According to gender variable, 48 (%80,0) of the teaching staff were male, 12 (%20,0) of them were female.

According to academic title variable, 5 (%8,3) of the teaching staff were Associate Professors, 18 (%30,0) were Assistant Professors, 17 (28,3) were instructors, 8 (%13,3) were lecturers, and 12 (%20,0) were Research Assistants.

According to age variable, 16 (%26,7) of the teaching staff were 20-30, 27 (%45,0) were 31-40, 17 (%28,3) were over 40.

According to year of service variable, 25 (%41,7) of the teaching staff were 1-5 years, 7 (%11,7) were 6-10 years, 16 (%26,7) were 11-15 years, 12 (%20,0) were over 15 years.

According to duration of administration variable, 32 (%53,3) of the teaching staff were none, 17 (%28,3) were 1-3 years, 11 (%18,3) were over 3 years.

According to administrative task variable, 22 (%36,7) of the teaching staff were yes, 38 (%63,3) of them were no.

According to hours of lesson variable, 4 (%6,7) of the teaching staff were 0, 17 (%28,3) were 0-15, 4 (%6,7) were 16-20, 10 (%16,7) were 21-25, and 25 (%41,7) were 26-30 hours.

According to marital status variable, 43 (%71,7) of the teaching staff were married, 17 (%28,3) of them were single.

Table 2: Teaching Staff's Correlation Between Perceived Organizational Attractiveness and Job Satisfaction Levels

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Organizational Attractiveness	Intrinsic Satisfaction	Extrinsic Satisfaction	General Satisfaction
Organizational Attractiveness	3,450	0,732	1,000			
Intrinsic Satisfaction	4,201	0,442	0,375**	1,000		
Extrinsic Satisfaction	3,683	0,656	0,456**	0,689**	1,000	
General Satisfaction	3,994	0,485	0,452**	0,920**	0,918**	1,000

Participating teaching staff's "organizational attractiveness" level has been determined as high (3,450 ± 0,732); "intrinsic satisfaction" level very high (4,201 ± 0,442); "extrinsic satisfaction" level high (3,683 ± 0,656); "general satisfaction" level high (3,994 ± 0,485).

It has been stated that there is a significant positive weak correlation between intrinsic satisfaction and organizational satisfaction ($r=0.375$; $p=0,003<0.05$). It has been stated that there is a significant weak positive correlation between extrinsic satisfaction and organizational attractiveness ($r=0.456$; $p=0,000<0.05$). It has been stated that there is a significant positive medium correlation between intrinsic satisfaction and extrinsic satisfaction ($r=0.689$; $p=0,000<0.05$). It has been stated that there is a significant weak positive correlation between general satisfaction and organizational satisfaction ($r=0.452$; $p=0,000<0.05$). It has been stated that there is a significant positive high correlation between general satisfaction and intrinsic satisfaction ($r=0.92$; $p=0,000<0.05$). It has been stated that there is a significant positive high correlation between general satisfaction and extrinsic satisfaction ($r=0.918$; $p=0,000<0.05$).

Table 3: Perceived Organizational Attractiveness's Effect on Job Satisfaction

Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	β	t	p	F	Model (p)	R ²
Intrinsic Satisfaction	Stable Organizational	3,421	13,203	0,000	9,465	0,003	0,125
	Satisfaction	0,226	3,077	0,003			
Extrinsic Satisfaction	Stable Organizational	2,272	6,149	0,000	15,229	0,000	0,194
	satisfaction	0,409	3,902	0,000			
General Satisfaction	Stable Organizational	2,962	10,824	0,000	14,871	0,000	0,190
	satisfaction	0,299	3,856	0,000			

Regression analysis which is conducted to determine the cause effect relationship between organizational satisfaction and intrinsic satisfaction has been found statistically significant ($F=9,465$; $p=0,003<0.05$). As determinant of intrinsic satisfaction level, it has been seen that its correlation with organizational satisfaction variables (explanatory power) is weak ($R^2=0,125$). The teaching staff's organizational satisfaction level increases intrinsic satisfaction level ($\beta=0,226$).

Regression analysis which is conducted to determine the cause effect relationship between organizational satisfaction and extrinsic satisfaction has been found statistically significant ($F=15,229$; $p=0,000<0.05$). As determinant of extrinsic satisfaction level, it has been seen that its correlation with organizational satisfaction variables (explanatory power) is weak ($R^2=0,194$). The teaching staff's organizational satisfaction level increases extrinsic satisfaction level ($\beta=0,409$).

Regression analysis which is conducted to determine the cause effect relationship between organizational satisfaction and general satisfaction has been found statistically significant ($F=14,871$; $p=0,000<0.05$). As determinant of general satisfaction level, it has been seen that its correlation with organizational satisfaction variables (explanatory

power) is weak ($R^2=0,190$). The teaching staff's organizational satisfaction level increases general satisfaction level ($\beta=0,299$).

Table 4: Teaching Staff's Perceived Organizational Satisfaction and Job Satisfaction Level's Comparison with Descriptive Features

Demographic Features	n	Organizational Satisfaction	Intrinsic Satisfaction	Extrinsic Satisfaction	General Satisfaction
School Worked		Median	Median	Median	Median
BitlisEren U	7	31,790(3,750)	27,570(4,083)	23,210(3,500)	24,860(3,950)
Karabük U	7	23,710(3,250)	37,570(4,417)	40,290(4,250)	40,070(4,400)
Batman U	10	27,650(3,250)	31,550(4,292)	35,450(3,938)	33,750(4,175)
Afyon U	8	29,060(3,500)	16,880(3,917)	17,380(3,313)	17,060(3,675)
Balıkesir U	8	28,440(3,500)	23,310(4,000)	27,310(3,500)	25,310(3,800)
Burdur U	6	25,580(3,125)	27,670(4,250)	20,750(3,563)	21,080(3,825)
Kırşehir U	14	39,390(3,875)	40,790(4,458)	39,210(4,000)	40,890(4,275)
$\chi^2_{kw} =$		5,704	12,718	14,467	15,350
p=		0,457	0,048	0,025	0,018
İleri Test (MWU)=			3>4, 7>4, 7>5 (p<0.05)	2>4, 3>4, 7>4, 7>6 (p<0.05)	7 > 1, 2 > 4, 3 > 4, 7 > 4, 7 > 5, 2 > 6, 7 > 6 (p<0.05)
Gender		Median	Median	Median	Median
Male	48	30,540(3,500)	28,170(4,167)	28,500(3,750)	28,110(3,925)
Female	12	30,330(3,375)	39,830(4,500)	38,500(4,000)	40,040(4,275)
MWU/Z=		286,000/-0,037	176,000/-2,078	192,000/-1,781	173,500/-2,118
p=		0,970	0,038	0,075	0,034
Academic Title		Median	Median	Median	Median
Assoc. Prof.	5	28,800(3,250)	30,300(4,333)	32,000(4,000)	30,500(4,200)
Asst. Prof	18	28,110(3,500)	31,640(4,375)	28,500(3,875)	29,750(3,975)
Instructor	17	29,970(3,500)	28,820(4,167)	34,120(3,875)	31,760(3,950)
Lecturer	8	41,380(3,750)	27,810(4,000)	28,620(3,563)	28,060(3,925)
Res Asst.	12	28,290(3,125)	33,040(4,417)	29,000(3,813)	31,460(4,200)
$\chi^2_{kw} =$		3,741	0,683	1,192	0,315
p=		0,442	0,953	0,879	0,989
Age		Median	Median	Median	Median
20-30	16	28,780(3,250)	29,160(4,292)	29,470(3,813)	29,190(4,075)
31-40	27	30,040(3,500)	34,540(4,333)	33,940(3,875)	34,500(4,150)
+ 40	17	32,850(3,500)	25,350(3,917)	26,000(3,500)	25,380(3,750)
$\chi^2_{kw} =$		0,489	3,038	2,251	2,972
p=		0,783	0,219	0,324	0,226
Year of Service		Median	Median	Median	Median
1-5 years	25	33,600(3,500)	33,440(4,417)	35,960(4,000)	34,660(4,200)
6-10 years	7	27,570(3,250)	36,140(4,417)	31,860(3,875)	35,860(4,200)
11-15 years	16	26,940(3,375)	28,310(4,125)	25,340(3,688)	26,250(3,900)
Over 15 years	12	30,500(3,500)	24,000(3,917)	25,210(3,438)	24,380(3,725)
$\chi^2_{kw} =$		1,671	3,379	5,019	4,508
p=		0,643	0,337	0,170	0,212

Duration of Administration		Median	Median	Median	Median
None	32	33,720(3,750)	30,660(4,208)	31,420(3,875)	31,140(4,100)
1-3 years	17	30,880(3,500)	34,090(4,333)	31,650(3,875)	32,470(4,050)
Over 3 years	11	20,550(3,000)	24,500(3,917)	26,050(3,375)	25,590(3,750)
$\chi^2_{KW} =$		4,728	2,034	0,885	1,131
$p =$		0,094	0,362	0,643	0,568
Administrative Task		Median	Median	Median	Median
Yes	22	29,250(3,500)	35,110(4,417)	33,500(3,875)	34,160(4,225)
No	38	31,220(3,500)	27,830(4,125)	28,760(3,750)	28,380(3,975)
MWU/Z=		390,500/-0,425	316,500/-1,563	352,000/-1,016	337,500/-1,236
$p =$		0,671	0,118	0,310	0,216
Hours of Lesson		Median	Median	Median	Median
0	4	35,380(3,625)	49,120(4,708)	36,380(3,813)	45,120(4,300)
0-15	17	27,710(3,250)	33,880(4,417)	36,000(4,000)	35,290(4,250)
16-20	4	46,620(4,250)	32,250(4,208)	28,880(3,750)	29,620(4,025)
21-25	10	28,300(3,500)	21,500(3,917)	23,250(3,563)	22,700(3,775)
26-30	25	29,920(3,500)	28,540(4,167)	28,980(3,625)	28,160(3,900)
$\chi^2_{KW} =$		4,398	8,262	4,117	6,551
$p =$		0,355	0,082	0,390	0,162
Marital Status		Median	Median	Median	Median
Married	43	29,860(3,500)	30,520(4,167)	29,650(3,750)	30,240(3,950)
Single	17	32,120(3,500)	30,440(4,250)	32,650(4,000)	31,150(4,100)
MWU/Z=		338,000/-0,454	364,500/-0,016	329,000/-0,601	354,500/-0,181
$p =$		0,650	0,987	0,548	0,857

5.1 School Worked

According to the results of Kruskal Wallis H-Test which is conducted to determine whether there is a significant difference between the mean scores of internal satisfaction scores and schools worked variable of the teaching staff participating in the research, the difference between means of the group has been found significant ($X^2_{KW} = 12,718$, $p = 0.048 < 0.05$). Mann Whitney U test has been applied in order to determine which group originated the difference. Accordingly, intrinsic satisfaction scores of Batman University teaching staff ($4,217 \pm 0,336$) has been found higher than worked school Afyon University's ($3,875 \pm 0,327$). Worked school Kırşehir University's teaching staff's intrinsic satisfaction scores ($4,464 \pm 0,448$) is higher than Afyon University's ($3,875 \pm 0,327$). Worked school Kırşehir University's teaching staff's intrinsic satisfaction scores ($4,464 \pm 0,448$) is higher than Balıkesir University's ($4,031 \pm 0,351$).

According to the results of Kruskal Wallis H-Test which is conducted to determine whether extrinsic satisfaction score means of the teaching staff show a

significant difference in terms of school worked variable, the difference between the mean scores of group has been found significant ($\chi^2_{KW}=14,467$; $p=0.025<0.05$). Mann Whitney U test has been applied in order to determine which group originated the difference. Accordingly, school worked Karabük University's teaching staff's extrinsic satisfaction scores ($4,054\pm 0,586$) is higher than Afyon University's ($3,313\pm 0,372$). School worked Batman University's teaching staff's extrinsic satisfaction scores ($3,875\pm 0,270$) are higher than Afyon University' ($3,313\pm 0,372$). School worked Kırşehir University's teaching staff's extrinsic satisfaction scores ($3,982\pm 0,745$) are higher than Afyon University's ($3,313\pm 0,372$). School worked Kırşehir University's teaching staff's extrinsic satisfaction scores ($3,982\pm 0,745$), are higher than Burdur University's ($3,250\pm 0,818$).

According to the results of Kruskal Wallis H-Test which is conducted to determine whether extrinsic satisfaction score means of the teaching staff show a significant difference in terms of school worked variable, the difference between the mean scores of group has been found significant ($\chi^2_{KW}=15,350$; $p=0.018<0.05$). Mann Whitney U test has been applied in order to determine which group originated the difference. Accordingly, school worked Kırşehir University's teaching staff's general satisfaction scores ($4,271\pm 0,536$) is higher than Bitlis Eren University's ($3,821\pm 0,527$). School worked Karabük University's teaching staff's general satisfaction scores ($4,257\pm 0,488$) are higher than Afyon University's ($3,650\pm 0,330$). Batman University's teaching staff's general satisfaction scores ($4,080\pm 0,281$) is higher than Afyon University's ($3,650\pm 0,330$). Kırşehir University's teaching staff's general satisfaction scores ($4,271\pm 0,536$), have been found higher than Afyon University's ($3,650\pm 0,330$). Kırşehir University's teaching staff's general satisfaction scores ($4,271\pm 0,536$) have been found higher than Balıkesir University's ($3,850\pm 0,407$). Karabük University's teaching staff's general satisfaction scores ($4,257\pm 0,488$) have been found higher than Burdur University's ($3,750\pm 0,469$). Kırşehir University's teaching staff's general satisfaction scores ($4,271\pm 0,536$) have been found higher than Burdur University's teaching staff general satisfaction scores ($3,750\pm 0,469$).

According to the results of tests which are conducted to determine whether mean of organizational attractiveness scores of participating teaching staff show a significant difference in terms of school worked variable, difference between means of group have not been found significant ($p>0,05$).

5.1 Gender

According to the results of Mann Whitney U Test which is conducted to determine whether intrinsic satisfaction score means of the teaching staff show a significant difference in terms of gender variable, the difference between the mean scores of groups

has been found significant (MWU=176,000; $p=0.038<0.05$). Intrinsic satisfaction scores of male participants ($x=4,146$), have been found lower than female's intrinsic satisfaction scores($x=4,424$).

According to the results of Mann Whitney U Test which is conducted to determine whether general satisfaction score means of the teaching staff participating in the research show a significant difference in terms of gender variable, the difference between the mean scores of groups has been found significant(MWU=173,500; $p=0.034<0.05$). Males' general satisfaction scores ($x=3,934$)have been found lower than females' scores ($x=4,233$).According to the results of tests which are conducted to determine whether mean of organizational attractiveness, extrinsic satisfaction scores of participating teaching staff show a significant difference in terms of school worked variable, difference between means of group have not been found significant ($p>0,05$).

According to the results of the test which are conducted to determine whether there is a meaningful difference in terms of organizational attractiveness, intrinsic satisfaction, extrinsic satisfaction, general satisfaction scores of academic staff participating in the research in terms of **academic title, age, year of service, duration of administration, administrative task, marital status** variables, the difference between the means of group scores have not been found significant ($p>0,05$).

6. Discussion/Result/Suggestion

The level of "organizational attractiveness" of the teaching staff participating in the research is high and "general satisfaction" is high. According to the findings obtained from the research, the job satisfaction of academic staff did not differ in terms of academic title, age, years of service, administration period, administrative duty, class hours, marital status. These results are in agreement with the results of some research conducted on the job satisfaction of the teaching staff (Kasapoğlu, 1999; Karlıdağvedig., 2000; Musalvedig., 1995; Oran, 1989; Çetinkanat, 2000; Esen, 2001; Heller vedig., 1993; Yıldızvedig., 2003; Öncel, 1998).When married and single teaching staff are compared to each other, while singles can spend more time on their business and academic development, married ones seem to earn more in terms of the social support they receive and the total monthly income that goes into their homes (Bilge vedig., 2007).In some studies, the level of job satisfaction of single teaching staff has been found higher than that of married (Dalkılıç, 2014; Ergin 1993). Although marital status has been considered to have a high correlation with job satisfaction (Clark, 1996), there are some findings in literature that contradict with correlation of job satisfaction and marital status. The means of organizational attractiveness and extrinsic satisfaction scores of the

teaching staff have not been found significant in terms of gender variable. Men's intrinsic satisfaction, general satisfaction scores have been found lower than women's intrinsic satisfaction scores. The findings that are obtained from studies analyzing teaching staff's job satisfaction according to gender do not show parallelism to each other. In some studies, while women's job satisfaction levels were found higher (Hodson, 1989; Kelly, 1989); in other studies, men's job satisfaction levels were found higher (Mccaslinve Mwangi, 1994; Friesen, Holdawayve Rice, 1983; Varca, Shaffer ve McCauley, 1983; Dalkılıç, 2014). Herzberg's work based on two factorial theories showed that all motivating factors outside responsibility increased women's job satisfaction, while extrinsic hygienic factors caused dissatisfaction. Some studies have shown that there is no difference in the job satisfaction of male and female teaching staff. Women teaching staff are seen to have conditions that are more equal with men who are similar to those who do not work or with women working in other sectors. For this reason, the job satisfaction of men and women may not be different (Bilge vediğ., 2007).

Kırşehir University's teaching staff's intrinsic satisfaction score have been found high. Afyon University's intrinsic satisfaction scores have been found low. Karabük University's extrinsic satisfaction score have been found high. Burdur University's extrinsic satisfaction score have been found low. The highest general satisfaction score mean belongs to Kırşehir University, which means it belongs to Central Anatolia Region, the following is Karabük University in Black Sea Region, university with the lowest general satisfaction scores belong to Afyon University in Aegean Region. The findings in another study do not show parallelism with findings in our study. It is emphasized that the academic staff working in the Marmara Region had the highest job satisfaction, followed by the Southeastern Anatolia Region and the lowest job satisfaction score was the academic staff working in the Mediterranean Region (Dalkılıç, 2014).

It is thought that the life comfort of teaching staff in Kırşehir University has a positive effect on the job satisfaction. In the study conducted by Ay and Avşaroğlu (2010), the findings overlap with our findings. There is a weak positive correlation between intrinsic satisfaction and organizational satisfaction. There is a weak positive correlation between extrinsic satisfaction and organizational satisfaction. There is a medium positive correlation between extrinsic satisfaction and intrinsic satisfaction. There is a weak positive correlation between general satisfaction and organizational attractiveness. There is a high positive correlation between general satisfaction and intrinsic satisfaction. There is a very high correlation between general satisfaction and extrinsic satisfaction. The teaching staff's organizational attractiveness (organization attraction) increases intrinsic satisfaction, extrinsic satisfaction and general satisfaction.

The workers evaluate their position in the institution positively in terms of organizational attractiveness and for this reason; it is possible to say that the relationship between person and institution is positive. Subsequent researchers can work on similar studies comparative organizational behavioral variables by expanding the target population of the study.

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